

Good practice guide on the measurement of power losses in non-oriented and grain-oriented steel sheets at frequencies ranging from DC up to 10 kHz using standard measurement setups at room temperature

Michal Ulvr¹, Franziska Weickert², Korbinian Pfnuer², Joachim Lüdke², Katja Hoffmann², Stuart Harmon³, Daniel Brunt³, Adam Wilson³, Massimo Pasquale⁴, Nicoleta Banu⁴, Luciano Rocchino⁴, Enzo Ferrara⁴, Fausto Fiorillo⁴, Ram Ramanathan Mathavan Jeyabalan⁵, Gaurang Vakil⁵

¹Czech Metrology Institute (CMI), Czech Republic

²Physikalisch-Technische Bundesanstalt (PTB), Germany

³ National Physical Laboratory (NPL), United Kingdom

⁴Instituto Nazionale di Ricerca Metrologica (INRIM), Italy

⁵ University of Nottingham (UNOTT), United Kingdom

Contents

1	Introduction	3
2	Units	3
3	NMI setups and uncertainty budgets description	3
3.1	Measurement setup at PTB	3
3.2	Measurement setup at CMI	5
3.3	Measurement setup at INRIM	8
3.4	Measurement setup at NPL	29
4	Measurement Challenges	32
5	Traceability	34
6	European capabilities for power losses	34
7	References	36

1 Introduction

Two experimental setups are currently used for the measurement of specific power losses in grain-oriented (GO) and non-oriented (NO) electrical steel – the Epstein frame and the single sheet tester (SST). Measurement of power losses at room temperature using Epstein frame up to 400 Hz is described in IEC 60404-2 [1] and up to 10 kHz in IEC 60404-10 [2]. Measurement of power losses at room temperature using SST is described in IEC 60404-3 [3] with no frequency range stated.

The IEC standards give rough guidelines for the measurement of power loss, but allows for individual realizations of the specific setups that all reach the same goal. This is supported by the results of the round robin comparison [4, 5] within the HEFMAG project that agree reasonably well within measurement uncertainties (MUs) for both, SST and Epstein data.

2 Units

The common SI unit used for magnetic polarization J_m is Tesla (T), for magnetic field strength H_m it is A/m and for specific power loss measurement P_s is W/kg and for specific apparent power S_s is VA.

But sometimes a different unit can be seen for specific power loss such as W/m^3 . In this case, just divide the result by the density of the sample (in kg/m^3). For example:

- measured $P_s = 2035 W/m^3$
- density of the sample is $7650 kg/m^3$
- converted $P_s = 0.266 W/kg$

3 NMI setups and uncertainty budgets description

3.1 Measurement setup at PTB

Figure 1 shows the block diagram of the hybrid (analog and digital) control utilized at PTB [6]. The input signal U_{in} is generated by a 16-bit wave form generator, and it is synchronized with two analog-to-digital converter (ADC) cards collecting data of the primary $I_1 = U_1 * R$ current and of the secondary U_2 voltage, respectively. Synchronization monitors the exact phase shift ϕ between U_{in} , U_1 and U_2 . After amplification with a home build power amplifier adapted to AC signals between 40 Hz and 1 kHz, the signal is fed into the magnetic circuit consisting of SST or Epstein frame. The combination of analog and digital feedback control loops enables to match U_2 to a sinusoidal signal with low distortion as required by standards [1,3]. The digital feedback control is based on fast Fourier analysis of the U_2 signal. After filtering of the fundamental wave and multiplication with a negative damping factor, the modified signal is added to U_{in} and as a result higher harmonics of U_2 are removed. Several iterations are carried out automatically by the software at each polarization value J to optimize the final output of U_2 . Further details of the experiment can be found elsewhere [1,7].

Figure 1: Block diagram for the measurement of magnetic losses in electrical steel sheets at PTB. The magnetic circuit consisting of SST or Epstein frame is enveloped by dashed lines [6].

Uncertainty budget for PTB measurements

The specific power loss P_S is estimated according to the standards [1,3]

$$P_S = \frac{N_1}{m_{eff}N_2} \cdot \frac{1}{T} \int_0^T I_1(t)U_2(t)dt \quad (1)$$

with N_1 and N_2 being the numbers of turns of primary and secondary windings of the Epstein frame or the SST, and T being one period $1/f$ of the measurement frequency f . Variable m_{eff} denotes the effective mass and it is calculated based on the mass m and length l of the sample and the effective magnetic length l_m

$$m_{eff} = m \frac{l_m}{l} \quad \text{for SST, and } m_{eff} = \frac{l_m}{4l} \quad \text{for Epstein frame measurements.}$$

The value of l_m is 0.94 m and 0.45 m for Epstein and SST respectively. In practice, all collected data points U_1 and U_2 are Fourier transformed into frequency domain and a phase correction is applied to remove phase shifts induced by the measurement electronics. Loss P is calculated directly by multiplication and consecutive addition

$$P = \frac{R \cdot N_1 \sum_{i=1}^N [Re(U_i) \cdot Re(U_i) + Im(U_i) \cdot Im(U_i)]}{N_2 \cdot 2m_{eff}} \quad (2)$$

of the complex Fourier coefficients of U_1 and U_2 . For a precise estimate of the measurement uncertainty (MU) of P_S , two correction terms are included to equation (2)

$$P_S = \frac{P(I_1, U_2)}{\left(\frac{f}{f_{tar}}\right)^2 \cdot \left(\frac{F}{\frac{\pi}{\sqrt{8}}}\right)^2} \cdot \left(\frac{J_{tar}}{J}\right)^\alpha \quad (3)$$

that account for the deviation of the form factor F from the ideal value $\pi/\sqrt{8}$ and the difference between measured polarization \hat{J} and target polarization \hat{J}_{tar} . Exponent α models the empiric

dependence $P_S \sim J^\alpha$. α is obtained by fitting of experimental data during the measurement. Correlations between quantities P_S , J , and the applied field H , lead to varying contributions to the combined MU of P_S as shown in Figure 2 for an Epstein frame measurement of a GO material at 100Hz up to 1.9T.

Figure 2: MU distribution of Epstein frame measurement on GO material at 100Hz. Note, all individual MU contributions are shown for $k = 2$ (95%) and added linearly.

3.2 Measurement setup at CMI

Figure 3 shows the block diagram of the total losses measurement using Epstein frame at CMI. The generated analog signal (DAC out – pins AO 1 and AO GND) from the data acquisition (DAQ) card is fed back to the analog DAQ input for sampling synchronization (ADC readback – pins AI 0 and AI 8) and to the power amplifier that feeds the primary winding of the Epstein frame (DUT). The flowing current is measured using a current shunt R and an analog DAQ input (ADC-H – pins AI 1 and AI SENSE). The induced voltage u_B on the secondary winding of the Epstein frame is attenuated by a programmable attenuator PA01 (home build) and applied to the analog DAQ input (ADC-B – pins AI 2 and AI GND). Attenuation – if optional – again controls the DAQ using its digital outputs. The digitized current (as voltage drop u_H on the current shunt) through the primary winding, the voltage u_B on the secondary winding and the back-read generated signal entering the power amplifier are read from the DAQ by a control software (Figure 4) in the computer. The DAQ is a multipurpose USB-6281 (NI) with an 18-bit A/D converter and an aggregate sampling rate of 500 kS/s, a 16-bit DAC, and a set of generic digital I/O ports. The model 7228 (AE Techron) power amplifier supplies the primary winding of the Epstein frame (700 or 100 turns).

According to IEC 60404-2 [1], the shape factor of the sine wave signal on the secondary of the Epstein frame must be maintained at $1.11 \pm 1\%$. This was achieved by using the iterative method with the P controller. Using the given SW, it is possible to set all parameters of the iteration loop (feedback), parameters of the measured sample and to determine the amount of total losses

of the measured sample including uncertainty. The software also displays the primary and secondary waveforms and the shape factor value of the secondary voltage.

Figure 3: Block diagram for the measurement of magnetic losses in electrical steel sheets at CMI by Epstein frame.

Figure 4: New measurement software and feedback control.

Uncertainty budget for CMI measurements

The amplitude of magnetic polarization J_m and specific power losses P_s are calculated according to the formula A.2 and A.3 described in Annex A of the standard IEC 60404-2. The uncertainty of the total losses measurement using CMI setup depends mainly on the uncertainty of the frequency, u_H and u_B measurement, on the uncertainty of the used current shunt value, on the repeatability and on the uncertainty of the attenuator PA01. Measured (calibrated) frequency characteristic of the PA01 is applied in *.json* file in the control software, so the correction of the PA01 can be made. The other sources of uncertainties, which were determined experimentally, are temperature influence and the mismatch uncertainty of the Epstein frame and the sample. The uncertainty budget for the loss measurement by Epstein frame using CMI setup is shown in Table 1a and Table 1b.

Source of uncertainty	Type of uncertainty	k-factor	std. uncertainty (%)
current shunt value	B	1	0.005
voltage u_B (DAQ)	B	1	0.05
voltage u_H (DAQ)	B	1	0.05
attenuator PA01	B	1	0.2
Frequency	B	1	0.01
temperature influence	B	1	0.05
mismatch uncertainty of the Epstein frame and the sample	B	1	0.06
set value of J_m	B	1	0.05
repeatability	A	1	0.1
total uncertainty	-	1	0.25
total expanded uncertainty	-	2	0.5

Table 1a: Example of the uncertainty budget using the CMI setup for power loss measurements at 50 Hz.

Source of uncertainty	Type of uncertainty	k-factor	std. uncertainty (%)
current shunt value	B	1	0.02
voltage u_B (DAQ)	B	1	0.10
voltage u_H (DAQ)	B	1	0.10
attenuator PA01	B	1	0.70
frequency	B	1	0.01
temperature influence	B	1	0.05
mismatch uncertainty of the Epstein frame and the sample	B	1	0.06
set value of J_m	B	1	0.05
repeatability	A	1	0.35
total uncertainty	-	1	0.80
total expanded uncertainty	-	2	1.6

Table 1b: Example of the uncertainty budget using the CMI setup for power loss measurements at 1000 Hz.

3.3 Measurement setup at INRIM

Measurements at low frequencies IEC 60404-2

The basic elements of the setup are: 1) An arbitrary function generator driven by PC; 2) A power amplifier with very low output impedance supplying the primary current $i_H(t)$; 3) A calibrated shunt R_H , whose voltage drop $u_H = R_H i_H$ is detected for the measurement of the applied magnetic field; 4) A mutual inductor M_a with primary and secondary windings connected in series opposition with the magnetizing and secondary windings of the magnetizer. The value of M_a is chosen in such a way that the air flux linked with the secondary winding of the magnetizer is fully compensated.; 5) A couple of identical low-noise amplifiers with same bandwidth, employed in case of low signals; 6) A high sampling rate large bandwidth digital oscilloscope, with 10-12bit minimum vertical resolution. Synchronous sampling for the different channels of the oscilloscope is required. 7) A developed on purpose software for signal handling and control and calculation of the relevant magnetic parameters.

The measuring standards require that the magnetic induction $B(t)$ in the test sample is maintained sinusoidal under all measuring conditions and magnetizers. Given the non-linearity of the ferromagnetic response, an appropriate feedback method must be devised. Hysteresis loop tracers are nowadays chiefly endowed with digital control of the induction rate. They typically work on the principle of generating by digital means the magnetic field waveform ensuring the desired $B(t)$ (or $J(t)$) time dependence, besides handling by means of a computing unit the measuring procedure and recording of data. Systems employing analog feedback are still in use in some cases and sometimes preferred, under the condition that the employed electronic components have excellent thermal stability, where real-time control of the magnetization is important. Analog-feedback DC loop tracers are delicate setups, traditionally developed and applied in basic research, which nowadays have given way to fully computer controlled systems, where both field generation and signal treatment are digitally handled. There are two basic ways of implementing digital feedback. One consists in trying to emulate by computation the real time control of the sample magnetization typically realized by means of analog feedback, the other in programming the suitable time dependence of magnetizing current by iterative augmentation of the input using an inverse approach. Computing requirements pose the basic limitation to the feedback chain bandwidth in real time control. The involved operations basically consist in: 1) Acquisition at given instants of time, separated by conveniently small intervals, and A/D conversion of a reference signal, describing the desired dB/dt waveform, and of the actual measured waveform; 2) Comparison of these two signals and computation, by means of a regulation algorithm, of the correct value of the magnetizing current, taking into account the composition of the primary circuit; 3) Digital-to-analog conversion and generation of the calculated current. It is expected that, with the application of increasingly fast Digital Signal Processor (DSP) cards, real time digital control will gain general acceptance, both in commercial and laboratory setups. At present, the iterative method is most commonly applied to achieve the desired $\dot{J}(t)$ trajectory [1, 8, 9]. It can be realized by adopting the scheme shown in Fig. 5, which describes in summary the general structure of a computer-controlled digital hysteresis loop tracer.

The operation of recursive digital control of $\dot{J}(t)$ starts with the generation of a function $e(t)$, normally similar to the desired induction derivative dB/dt . The magnetizing winding is then supplied by a current $i_H(t)$ via a power amplifier used as a voltage amplifier with resistive-inductive load. Safe operation of the power amplifier in face of possible overvoltages at the output (which could turn up when working in current mode) is ensured in this way. The calibrated resistor R_H provides then a voltage drop $u_H(t)$ proportional to the magnetic field strength, which is detected and A/D converted, at least over one full period, together with the signal $u_2(t) = -N_2 A \cdot dB/dt$ on the secondary winding. A two-channel digital oscilloscope or an acquisition card performing synchronous acquisition can be used to this purpose. These devices are characterized by input impedance typically around 1 M Ω or higher and do not load the secondary circuit. Multiplexing is not recommended, as it introduces time delay between channels. ADC converters with higher than 10-bit resolution are possibly employed, depending on the measuring frequency, and synchronous triggering over the two channels with interchannel delay and trigger jitter both lower than 10⁻¹⁰ s is

generally available. To improve the signal-to-noise ratio, a large number of sampled points per period (normally more than 10^3) is taken. This also makes negligible the error made in the measurement of the loop area, when the elementary time intervals have duration not commensurable with the magnetization period. It is also important, depending on the degree of control of the induction rate, when rectangular loops have to be measured. For maximum accuracy of the numerical integration, the trapezoidal rule or the Simpson's rule are typically applied. At low frequencies, around or below 1 Hz, the secondary signal is small and needs to be amplified by a DC-coupled, variable gain, very stable low noise amplifier. Commercial high-quality devices are usually endowed with RC filtering and may introduce small phase shifts. Consequently, both $u_H(t)$ and $u_2(t)$ should be passed through the same amplifier types (though usually with very different gains). The digitized and recorded signals are then stored into a PC, where integration is performed, the residual offsets and drifts are numerically eliminated and, in the absence of automatic compensation, correction for the air-flux is made. Thermal stability of the amplifiers is mandatory for meaningful linear drift compensation of the induction signal. Both $H(t)$ and $J(t)$ are thus calculated and the suitable adjustments on the magnetizing current strength are made in order to attain the desired peak value J_p of the magnetic polarization. The time functions $H(t)$ and $J(t)$ can be regarded as parametric representations of a hysteresis loop bearing a substantial similarity with the final loop. By changing $H(t)$, we expect that $J(t)$ will be modified as dictated by the behavior of the function $H(B)$. It is an easy matter to compute such a function, that is the field $H(t)$ depending on time in such a way that $J(t)$, turns out to be identical to the desired one. A novel $e(t)$ function can accordingly be calculated, programmed into the arbitrary function generator and delivered to the power amplifier. To this end, the equation of the primary circuit is considered, which can be written, according to the scheme in Figure 5, as

$$Ge(t) = u_G(t) = (R_s + R_H) \cdot i_H(t) + N_1 A \frac{dJ}{dt} \quad (4),$$

where G is the gain of the power amplifier, $(R_s + R_H)$ is the resistance of the whole primary circuit, including the winding resistance, A is the cross-sectional area of the sample, and the air-flux enclosed by the primary winding is disregarded. If the magnetic path length l_m is defined, the current $i_H(t)$ in this equation is related to the programmed field according to the usual equation $i_H(t) = H(t)N_1 / l_m$. In those cases where the air-flux contribution cannot be neglected, the voltage $u_L(t)$ (Fig. 5) is better expressed as $u_L(t) = N_1(A \frac{dJ}{dt} + A_t \mu_0 \frac{dH}{dt})$, with A_t the total area enclosed by magnetizing winding. An example of measured relationship between $u_G(t)$, $u_R(t)$, and $u_L(t)$ under controlled sinusoidal induction is reported in Figure 6 for the case of a non-oriented Fe-Si lamination tested in an Epstein frame at a frequency of 0.5 Hz and peak polarization value $J_p = 1.32$ T. After the so calculated $e(t)$ function is generated, signal acquisition and calculation of $H(t)$ and $J(t)$ are repeated. Normally, the process is not concluded in a single step and $e(t)$ is re-calculated and applied again. Iteration will proceed till the desired $J(t)$ behavior is achieved, as objectively judged, for example, from the deviation of the actual value of the form factor from the theoretical one. To be remarked that this feedback procedure, being based on analytical considerations regarding the loop shape, is in principle independent of the specific magnetizing frequency and is free of auto-oscillatory behavior. To improve accuracy and speed of the feedback process, the reactive and the resistive terms in Eq. (4) should possibly be of comparable values. At very low magnetizing frequencies this calls for increased mass of the specimen and reasonably low values of R_s and R_H .

Figure 5: Basic scheme of a hysteresisgraph-wattmeter based on the fluxmetric principle for the measurement of hysteresis loop and energy losses as a function of frequency in soft magnetic materials. The periodic magnetizing current $i_H(t)$ is supplied to the primary winding by the power amplifier via the anti-inductive resistors R_S and R_H . The latter is a calibrated shunt, whose voltage drop $u_H(t)$ is proportional to the magnetizing field $H(t)$. Air-flux compensation is automatically achieved by means of the mutual inductance M_a . $u_H(t)$ and the secondary voltage $u_2(t)$ are amplified, if required, fed into a digital oscilloscope, A/D converted and suitably transformed by software in the required measuring quantities. A prescribed time dependence of the magnetic polarization $J(t)$ (that is of the secondary voltage $u_2(t)$) is obtained by means of a digitally controlled recursive technique, eventually driving the signal generator with the appropriate time function. This specific setup with power amplifiers is also suitable for low frequency measurements and use with samples of low cross-section and mass.

Figure 6: Sinusoidal flux derivative is imposed in NO steel sheets tested by the Epstein method with recursive digital control of the secondary voltage.

Measurements at high frequencies. IEC60404-10 (Epstein), IEC 60404-6 (ring samples).

There is an increasing trend towards the use of electrical machines and various types of devices over a wide range of frequencies and with a variety of supply methods, which call for the precise characterization of soft magnetic materials beyond the assessed DC and power frequency domain. There are indeed many kinds of excitation methods, which impose, within broad frequency limits, not only sinusoidal flux conditions, but also different types of rated voltage waveforms, with and without bias field, or pulsed magnetization (either with determined current or voltage pulses). While there are no special additional difficulties in setting up a system by which one can drive a particular type of excitation, many problems come around with the increase of the frequency. They can be faced by means of a rigorous approach to the measuring principles and their implementation in the testing operations. But to adapt the conventional measuring setups to the characterization of soft magnets up to the MHz range might become a relatively complex task. We shall discuss here the main potential difficulties and problems arising with the increase of the magnetizing frequency, in the limit where electromagnetic propagation phenomena are still irrelevant, that is up to frequencies where wavelengths are much larger than the size of the region occupied by the specimen. The flux penetration in the test sample can be incomplete (skin effect). This effect can be evaluated by calculating the skin depth $\delta = \sqrt{2/(\mu_0\mu_r\sigma\omega)}$, where μ_r is the relative permeability, that is the depth in the sample where the induction value falls by a factor $1/e$ with respect to the induction value at the surface. Under these conditions, thickness-dependent instead of intrinsic properties are measured. The skin effect can equally occur in the conductors and increase their AC resistance, often prompting the use of windings made of copper strips or multiconductor Litz wire. It has troublesome consequences when it affects the calibrated resistor R_H employed in the primary circuit as current probe. The frequency response of R_H should therefore be verified before starting the measurements. Wirewound resistors are not recommended in general, while carbon resistors can display a flat response till 10 - 20 MHz. Proximity effects, that is the interaction existing between closely placed conductors carrying an AC current, can also add to the skin effect in giving rise to an increase of the resistance of windings and leads.

1) The temperature of the sample can appreciably rise during the measurement. A 0.050 mm thick grain-oriented sheet, suitably developed for high-frequency applications, can display, for example, a power loss of about 500 W/kg at 1.0 T and 10 kHz. The sample temperature is correspondingly expected to rise at a rate around 1 °C/s. In a Mn-Zn ferrite tested at 1 MHz and peak polarization $J_p = 0.1$ T, sample heating can proceed at a rate higher than 2 °C/s. Excessive heating is obviously detrimental to the measuring accuracy, because the physical properties of the material can rapidly change with the temperature. This should be measured by placing a micro-thermocouple in contact with the specimen, which, in turn, should be suitably cooled, for example by keeping it into an oil bath. If the specimen is encapsulated, the junction shall be put in contact with the core material by making a small hole in the container. The method of single-shot acquisition and digital control of the measurement is the most appropriate when looking for minimum temperature increase, because the time interval where the sample is excited is minimum.

Figure 7: Hysteresis loops at given peak polarization $J_p = 100$ mT versus magnetizing frequency (dc – 1.8 MHz) in Mn-Zn N30 ring samples.

2) The increase of the required exciting power $P(t) = u_G(t) \cdot i_H(t)$ with the frequency poses serious limitations on the achievable peak polarization value. Under most circumstances of high-frequency testing, the characterization of the material for J_p not far from the knee of the magnetization curve can only be done under pulse excitation [10]. To make an example, a Mn-Zn ring of average diameter 50 mm and cross-sectional area $A = 50$ mm² requires about 100 VA peak power to be excited at $J_p = 0.1$ T at the frequency of 1 MHz. The general trend is one of using small cores with few primary turns, to limit the primary voltage. The number of turns of the secondary winding is equally small, but full coupling is to be ensured with the magnetizing winding, which must then be uniformly wound along the core [11]. As a rule, testing is made on ring shaped specimens. If single strips are to be characterized, a flux-closing yoke should be devised whose soft magnetic behavior associates with minimum skin effect. This condition is expectedly satisfied by a double-C core made by assembling mumetal or amorphous tapes of as low a thickness as practical. It has been shown that with such an arrangement, where the field strength is determined either by means of an H -coil or by measuring the magnetizing current and adopting a magnetic path length equal to the internal yoke diameter, measurements on amorphous strips can be reliably carried out up to 100 kHz [3]. To be noted that it would be very difficult to overcome this frequency limit with H -coils, as they are inevitably affected by substantial self-capacitances.

3) Fast A/D converters are required to satisfy our requirement of single-shot signal acquisition and real time analysis. This implies a certain limitation in signal amplitude resolution and if we are to make a complete characterization starting from DC properties, an acquisition device (for example a digital oscilloscope or a VXI system) with high resolution and relatively low sampling rate can be employed in the lower frequency range, to be substituted by a faster one with lower resolution at high frequencies. This makes sense, because the contribution to the measuring uncertainty coming from the uncertainty in the phase shift φ between fundamental component of the magnetizing current

and secondary voltage (i.e. on the phase shift $\varphi_{JH} = \frac{\pi}{2} - \varphi$ between the fundamental component of

the field and the polarization), whose minimization calls for a high number of sampling points and high amplitude resolution, is dominant only at low frequencies. The example shown in Figure 7 on the evolution with frequency of the hysteresis loops and the phase shift φ_{JH} in a Mn-Zn sintered ferrite puts in evidence that the resolution features required to the A/D converters in order to precisely measure the loop area are the more demanding the lower is the frequency. These results, in particular, have been obtained by making signal acquisition by means of a 500 Msample/s digital oscilloscope having amplitude resolution decreasing, together with the sampled time window, from

14-bits to 8-bits. The record length is correspondingly decreased from 5000 points to 150 points minimum at 1 MHz.

4) With the increase of the magnetizing frequency above the kHz range, it becomes important to consider the role of stray inductances and capacitances. This is a most basic issue, the one making the real difference between low-frequency and high-frequency measurements, at least up to the radiofrequency domain, where the wavelength of the electromagnetic field becomes comparable with the dimensions of the test specimen. We need to reduce the effect of the stray parameters to the largest possible extent, if we wish to determine the $J(H)$ behavior as we do it in the low frequency regime, without specific constraints regarding the non-linear behavior of the material. Under many practical circumstances, however, we might be essentially interested in the weak field response of the test sample, or simply in its behavior as an inductor, and correction for the effect of the stray parameters of windings and connecting cables can be attempted.

Figure 8: (TOP) Schematic description of the setup for the characterization of soft magnets at medium and high frequencies. Primary and secondary windings are laid down as a single bifilar layer, with well-separated turns. A digital voltmeter or a digital oscilloscope can be employed for synchronous two-channel signal acquisition. The calibrated resistor R_H is physically located close to the leads of the magnetizing winding and the shielded cables, which connect R_H and the secondary winding with the acquisition device, are as short as possible. Notice that the low-potential lead of the primary winding is separated from the ground by R_H . (BOTTOM) Board with toroidal ferrite sample (Blue). Notice evenly spaced 6 H windings (blue wire) and dB/dt (green wire) to reduce interwinding capacitance and short twisted leads/RG58 cables leading to the oscilloscope to reduce stray capacitances.

While the effect of leakage inductances, that is spurious flux linkages with windings and winding leads, can be generally kept negligible with respect to the flux generated by the magnetization in the material by closely fitting the windings on the magnetic core, and using short leads, the capacitance related effects require special consideration. Any winding is endowed with self-capacitance, which increasingly tends to drain current with increasing the frequency. This effect is reinforced by interwinding capacitance and capacitance in the connecting cables and at the input of the acquisition device. For example, a coaxial cable has a self-capacitance of the order of 50 - 100 pF/m, while the

input impedance of a digital voltmeter or oscilloscope is typically around 1 M Ω with a capacitance around 10 pF - 50 pF in parallel. The self-capacitances C_1 and C_2 of primary and secondary windings of the standard 700-turn Epstein frame can be of the order of 50 pF - 200 pF, much lower than the interwinding capacitance C_0 , which can be as high as 1000 pF - 3000 pF. Interposing an electrostatic screen between the windings and connecting it to the ground can eliminate the effect of C_0 , resulting, however, in a correspondingly enhanced value of C_1 and C_2 . For magnetic sheet and strip testing beyond 400 Hz this frame should be substituted, according to the Standard IEC 60404-10, by a 200-turn frame, which is deemed appropriate till 10 kHz [12]. Because of the reduced number of turns, the effect of interwinding capacitance can be minimized by laying out primary and secondary windings, which have the same number of turns, as a bifilar single layer with suitably spaced conductors. In this way, neighboring conductors are at the same potential and current leakage at high frequencies in the interposed dielectric is largely prevented. It is estimated that $C_0 \sim 300$ pF.

To reduce both self and mutual capacitances of the windings and the related dielectric losses, not only must some space be allowed between successive turns, but the dielectric material lying beneath the conductors must have low permittivity. Polystyrene could be such a material, by which the sample holder can be made. With ferrite cores, it is the test material itself that happens to be endowed with a high value of the dielectric constant, thereby favoring capacitive coupling between the neighboring winding turns. To limit this effect, a low permittivity dielectric tape should be wound beforehand on the core. Figure 8 provides a qualitative description of the arrangement of connections and windings in a setup for the characterization of a soft magnetic cores at medium and high frequencies. Bifilar single-layer windings are used and the connections are made by means of shielded cables. These cables should be short, as a rule, that is, of the order of few centimeters at most in the MHz range, to minimize the associated capacitances. Also the resistor R_H should be connected to the magnetizing winding by a very short lead. Since the sample is flux-closed, there are no stray-fields generated by it and the value of R_H is not perturbed. Because N_1 and N_2 can be very low at high frequencies, the effect of coupling between the fictitious primary and secondary single turns located along the median circumference of the ring specimen could be appreciated. This effect should therefore be checked and possibly compensated.

An acceptable simplification in the analytical treatment of power loss and apparent power at high frequencies is obtained by treating the material as a linear medium. It is possible in this case to generalize the basic concept of permeability, defined as the ratio $\mu=B/H$ between induction and field strength when the material is taken along the normal curve, in order to account for the AC hysteresis. Because of energy dissipation, induction lags in time behind the field and with $H(t) = H_p \cos(\omega t)$ we can assume $B(t) = B_p \cos(\omega t - \delta)$ under combined low peak induction values and high frequencies. We can then describe $B(t) = B_p \cos(\delta) \cos(\omega t) + B_p \sin(\delta) \sin(\omega t)$ as the sum of two 90° phase-shifted sinusoids of peak amplitude $B_1 = B_p \cos(\delta)$ and $B_2 = B_p \sin(\delta)$. Equivalently, we can write, using the complex notation, $H(t) = H_p e^{j\omega t}$ and $B(t) = B_p e^{j(\omega t - \delta)}$. The 90°-delayed component of the induction is evidently connected with the dissipation of energy. From the definition of power loss per unit volume we obtain

$$P = f \int_0^T H(t) \frac{dB}{dt} dt = f \pi H_p B_p \sin \delta \quad [\text{J/m}^3] \quad (5).$$

On the other hand, we can apply the definition of permeability to both in-phase and 90° out-of-phase components of $B(t)$

$$\mu' = \left(\frac{B_p}{H_p} \right) \cos \delta \quad \mu'' = \left(\frac{B_p}{H_p} \right) \sin \delta \quad (6).$$

μ' and μ'' can be viewed as the components of a complex quantity

$$\mu = \frac{B_p e^{j(\omega t - \delta)}}{H_p e^{j\omega t}} = \mu' - j\mu'' \quad (7)$$

Figure 9: (a) Equivalent R - L series circuit of the real inductor, where the resistance R_s lumps the effect of iron loss. The quality factor of the inductor is given by the ratio $Q = \omega L_s / R_s = 1/\tan \delta$. (b) Equivalent R - L parallel circuit. R_p and ωL_p are related to ωL_s and ωL_s by Eq. (11) and $Q = R_p/\omega L_p$. (c) If the stray capacitance C_p is taken into account, the measurements provide values R'_s and $\omega L'_s$, to be corrected in order to obtain the true values R_s and ωL_s .

and take accordingly the name of real and imaginary permeability, respectively. It is immediate to see that power loss per unit volume and imaginary permeability are related by the equation

$$P = f\pi H_p^2 \mu'' \quad (8).$$

Thus, the sole hypothesis of linearity permits us to describe the dynamic magnetic behavior of the material by means of the complex permeability. On very general grounds, one can additionally state that μ' and μ'' are not independent, but are related by a definite analytical relationship (Kramers-Kronig relations). The standard characterization of soft ring samples with the methods described in this Section provides us with the magnetic parameters of the material we are interested in: P , B_p , H_p , δ , μ' , μ'' . We can use them to define the electrical properties of the inductor under testing. For example, the ratio between the imaginary and real permeabilities can serve as a measure of the departure of an inductor with ferromagnetic core from a pure reactance. Such a ratio is, according to Eq. (6),

$$\frac{\mu''}{\mu'} = \tan \delta \quad (9).$$

The quantity $\tan \delta$, called “loss factor”, coincides with the inverse of the quality factor Q of the inductor. The latter is defined, in fact, as the ratio $Q = 2\pi(E_L/E_R)$, where $E_L = (1/2)B_p H_p \cos \delta$ and $E_R = \pi B_p H_p \sin \delta$ are the maximum stored energy and the energy dissipated during one cycle per unit volume of the material, respectively.

A real inductor can be described by means of the R - L series circuit shown in Fig. 9a, where the resistor R_s lumps the effect of iron loss and the winding resistance is neglected. For a ring core of average diameter D and cross-sectional area A , provided with a winding of N turns, the equivalent resistance R_s and reactance ωL_s turn out to be related to the imaginary and real permeabilities according to the equations:

$$R_s = \omega N^2 \frac{A}{\pi D} \mu'' \quad \omega L_s = \omega N^2 \frac{A}{\pi D} \mu' \quad (10)$$

and the quality factor is $Q = 1/\tan \delta = \omega L_s / R_s$. A parallel R - L equivalent circuit as shown in Fig. 9b, can equally be adopted, where the parallel resistance R_p and the parallel reactance ωL_p are related to their series counterpart by the equations

$$R_p = \frac{R_s^2 + \omega^2 L_s^2}{R_s} \quad \omega L_p = \frac{R_s^2 + \omega^2 L_s^2}{\omega L_s} \quad (11)$$

and the quality factor is correspondingly expressed as $Q = R_p/\omega L_p$. The complete equivalent circuit should actually contain also the stray capacitance and the modified R-L series circuit shown in Figure 9c should in this case more appropriately be adopted. The values R'_s and $\omega L'_s$ provided by the measurement should therefore be corrected in order to obtain the true values R_s and ωL_s .

The measurements at high frequencies on soft magnetic materials are recognized by the IEC 60404-6 standard, which deals, in particular, with the characterization of ring samples between 20 Hz and 200 kHz. The recommended measuring procedures are either the volt-amperometric method, as described by the IEC 60404-2, IEC 60404-3, and IEC 60404-10 for the Epstein and single sheet samples, or the LCR digital meter. The latter approach is based on the validity of the electrical equivalent, with the sample playing the role of a real inductor and the loss is incorporate in a resistive contribution to the circuit. This amounts to accept a linear description of the magnetic characteristic. The IEC 60404-6 Standard contains recommendations for reducing the additional losses and stray parameters, including the wire winding technique and the instrumentation. Wire insulated with a material having a low dielectric loss, for instance polytetrafluorethylene (PTFE) or polyethylene, should be used to minimise the effect of dielectric loss. Where possible, the magnetizing and secondary windings should be separated to reduce the interwinding capacitance. The connecting leads from the secondary winding to the measuring instruments should have low dielectric loss insulation and should be kept as short as practicable. The measuring instruments should have a low input capacitance and high input resistance to avoid loading the secondary winding.

High Temperature Measurements

The ambient temperature prescribed by the IEC 60404 standards is 23 \pm 5 degrees, this parameter should be carefully controlled as temperature shifts greater than $\pm 2^\circ\text{C}$ may increase the uncertainty significantly (0.2-0.5%), so it is recommended to check ambient temperature stability during the tests, and avoid temperature differences or drifts. The material under test may also warm up due to the tests so it is important to repeat the measurements after intermediate pauses which allow the sample to return to ambient temperature. Similarly, measurements under different ambient conditions (obtained in a cryostat, oven or climate chamber should also maintain the target temperature within $\pm 1^\circ\text{C}$. After an ambient temperature change, it should be ensured that the sample temperature matches the ambient one by suitable thermalization period (e.g. 1 hour at constant ambient temperature). Insulated wires with coating of appropriate grade (at least 155 $^\circ\text{C}$, F class IEC-60085, IEC 60034-1) may be used. Sample and coil supports (i.e. Epstein frame, ring holders etc) can be built with Polyimide or Polyether ether ketone materials for temperatures in the -60°C to 250°C range. The polymers need to be stabilized by annealing at the target temperature before use, and performance should be verified at room temperature. A slight increase in uncertainty is expected due coil and sample expansion and deformation.

The INRIM wattmeter-hysteresisgraph

The setup: scheme and basic hardware.

The wattmeter-hysteresisgraph developed at INRIM for the characterization of soft magnetic materials must comply with the requirements posed by the participation of the lab in the Calibration and Measurement Capabilities database at BIPM, a file gathering the physical quantities whose determination by any participating lab is recognized by all countries signatories of the Mutual Recognition Agreement. In order to declare and maintain such capabilities, the lab must satisfy the rules imposed by a certified quality system, regarding the whole lab and the specific measuring setup. The quantities measured by means of the INRIM wattmeter that appear in the CMC declaration are listed in Table 2. These are: 1) Specific power loss; 2) Specific apparent power; 3) AC magnetic polarization; 4) Magnetic field strength; 5) Peak permeability. For each of these

quantities, the following specifications must be provided: 1) Instrument or artefact; 2) Method of measurement; 3) Measuring range; 4) Measurement parameters; 5) Expanded measuring uncertainty. We will show in the following how we can cover such specifications, according to the Standards, with the selected instrumentation and the developed software.

Calibration or Measurement Service			Measurand Level or Range			Measurement Conditions/Independent Variable		Expanded uncertainty			
Quantity	Instrument or Artifact	Method of measurement	Minimum value	Maximum value	Units	Parameter	Specifications	Value	Coverage factor	Level of Confidence	Is the expanded uncertainty a relative one?
Soft magnetic sheet materials: specific power loss and apparent power	Epstein, ring and single sheet sample	Hysteresisgraph-wattmeter (IEC 60404-2, IEC 60404-3, IEC60404-6, IEC 60404-10)	5.00E-03	200	W/kg	Frequency	1 Hz to 10 kHz	10E-03 to 50E03	2	95%	Yes
						Polarisation	0.2 T to 1.8 T				
						Sample mass	> 0.1 kg				
						Primary current	< 15 A				
Soft magnetic sheet materials: specific apparent power	Epstein, ring and single sheet sample	Hysteresisgraph-wattmeter (IEC 60404-2, IEC 60404-3, IEC60404-6, IEC 60404-10)	5.00E-03	200	VA/kg	Frequency	1 Hz to 10 kHz	20E-03 to 80E03	2	95%	Yes
						Polarisation	0.2 T to 1.8 T				
						Sample mass	> 0.1 kg				
						Primary current	< 15 A				
Soft magnetic sheet materials: value of AC magnetic polarisation	Epstein, ring and single sheet sample	Mean value voltmeter (IEC60404-6 e IEC 60404-10)	0.05	2	T	Frequency	1 Hz to 10 kHz	4E-03 to 1,5E-02	2	95%	Yes
						Primary current	< 15 A				
Soft magnetic sheet materials: value of magnetic field strength	Epstein, ring and single sheet sample	Hysteresisgraph-wattmeter/ballistic setup (IEC 60404-2, IEC 60404-3, IEC 60404-4, IEC60404-6, IEC 60404-10)	0.5	10000	A/m	Frequency	DC to 10 kHz	4E-03 to 1,6E-02	2	95%	Yes
						Primary current	< 15 A				
Soft magnetic sheet materials: peak permeability	Epstein, ring, and single sheet sample	Hysteresisgraph-wattmeter/ballistic setup (IEC 60404-2, IEC 60404-3, IEC 60404-4, IEC60404-6, IEC 60404-10)	1.00E-04	1.00E-01	H/m	Frequency	DC to 10 kHz	5E-03 to 5E-02	2	95%	Yes
						Polarisation	0.2 T to 1.8 T				
						Sample mass	> 0.1 kg				
						Primary current	< 15 A				

Table 2: Calibration and Measurement Capabilities covered by the INRIM wattmeter-hysteresisgraph. Five different quantities are declared, making reference to the pertaining Standards and providing the measuring range, the measuring conditions, and the expanded uncertainty.

Let us therefore turn to the wattmeter scheme of Figure 5 and the features of the correspondingly employed instrumentation. Figure 10 provides a view of the whole setup, including the Epstein and the SST magnetizers. The following main elements are identified: 1) Arbitrary function generator Agilent 33220A; 2) NF-HS4052 power amplifier; 3) Calibrated shunt; 4) Epstein frame; 5) SST magnetizer with incorporated mutual inductor; 6) SRS low-noise signal amplifiers; 7) LeCroy HDO4054 4-channel oscilloscope; 8) Dual-channel Keysight 33522A function generator; 9) Kepco BOP 50-20MG power amplifier; 10) NF 4520 power amplifier. The power amplifiers 9) and 10) cover specific needs for high currents and high voltages, respectively, which cannot be satisfied with the NF-HS4052 power amplifier. We provide here details regarding the employed devices.

Figure 10: Overall view of the INRIM wattmeter-hysteresisgraph, realized according to the scheme of Figure 5. It consists of the following main elements: 1) Arbitrary function generator Agilent 33220A; 2) NF-HS4052 power amplifier; 3) Calibrated shunt; 4) Epstein frame with incorporated mutual inductor; 5) SST magnetizer with incorporated mutual inductor; 6) SRS low-noise signal amplifiers; 7) LeCroy HDO4054 4-channel oscilloscope; 8) Dual-channel Keysight 33522A function generator; 9) Kepco BOP 50-20MG power amplifier.

1) *Arbitrary function generator Agilent 33220A*. It can generate custom waveforms of a periodic function. Driven via GPIB interface. Output impedance 50Ω , signal amplitude from 20 mV pp to 20 Vpp into open circuit, harmonic distortion from -70 dB to -50 dB. 14-bit resolution, sampling rate of 50 MSa/s, 64 000 points maximum for arbitrary waveforms in the frequency range 1 Hz – 6 MHz. Trigger output TTL compatible, pulse width > 400 ns, maximum rate 1 MHz. Operating temperature $0^\circ\text{C} - 50^\circ\text{C}$.

2) *Power amplifier NF HS-4052*. Frequency range: DC – 500 kHz. Maximum output voltage for load resistance $R_L = 150 \Omega$: $\pm 150 V_{\text{peak}}$ (DC – 50 kHz); $\pm 55 V_{\text{peak}}$ (50 kHz – 500 kHz). Maximum output current: $\pm 5.66 A_{\text{peak}}$ (40 Hz – 200 kHz); $\pm 1 A_{\text{peak}}$ (DC - 40 Hz); Voltage gain in steps: 20, 40, 100, 200.

3) *Calibrated shunts*. These resistors are connected in series with the primary winding for

measuring the magnetizing field via the voltage drop: $H = u_H \cdot \frac{N_1}{R_H l_m}$ (see Fig. 5).

Tinsley resistors of values $R_H = 5 \text{ } \Lambda$ and $10 \text{ } \Lambda$ cover the most of the performed

measurements up to a few kHz. They have the following specifications: value uncertainty ± 10 ppm; temperature coefficient: $< 1 \text{ ppm}/^\circ\text{C}$; long-term stability: $\pm 5 \text{ ppm/year}$; operating temperature: $15 \text{ }^\circ\text{C} - 40 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. These resistors are subjected to periodic calibration by the Electrical Metrology lab of INRIM (Tags: IEN-MA-ZSR-008 and IEN-MA-ZSR-002, Technical procedure PT-ME-04-T-04). For high-currents and high-frequencies, packages of conventional anti-inductive resistors are used. Their frequency response is verified by means of an LCR analyser. They show a flat response versus frequency, with phase shift due to stray inductance of the order of 2° at 1 MHz. The precise resistance value is obtained with a four-point resistance measurement, carried out by use of the reference multimeter Agilent 3458A. It operates for this measurement with 5.5 digit resolution. Maximum sensitivity is $10 \text{ } \Lambda. 2 \text{ ppm}$ accuracy. This instrument is subjected to periodic calibration by the Electrical Metrology lab of INRIM (Tag: IEN-MA-ZNM-001, Technical procedure PT-ME-10-T-05).

INRIM ISTITUTO NAZIONALE DI RICERCA METROLOGICA		APPARECCHIATURE - SCHEDA EQUIPMENT - FORM	QT05_M03 Rev. 00 Pag. 1/2 Non controllato se stampato Uncontrolled if printed
DENOMINAZIONE:	Resistore campione a 4 terminali		
Id. COSTRUTTORE:	s/n 1959601		
Id. ULTERIORE:	IEN-MA-ZSR-008		
DESCRIZIONE:	Resistenza necessaria per misurare la corrente elettrica campione Classe di precisione 30 ppm valori di targa - 5 ohm / 1,4 A		
MODELLO/TIPO:	1659	INVENTARIO:	if
COSTRUTTORE:	Tinsley	UBICAZIONE:	Laboratorio MM (D; 208)
PROPRIETARIO:	INRIM	MESSA IN SERVIZIO:	2015
ELEMENTI:	Non applicabile		

INRIM ISTITUTO NAZIONALE DI RICERCA METROLOGICA		APPARECCHIATURE - SCHEDA EQUIPMENT - FORM	QT05_M03 Rev. 00 Pag. 1/2 Non controllato se stampato Uncontrolled if printed
DENOMINAZIONE:	Resistore campione a 4 terminali		
Id. COSTRUTTORE:	s/n 1959601		
Id. ULTERIORE:	IEN-MA-ZSR-008		
DESCRIZIONE:	Resistenza necessaria per misurare la corrente elettrica campione Classe di precisione 30 ppm valori di targa - 5 ohm / 1,4 A		
MODELLO/TIPO:	1659	INVENTARIO:	if
COSTRUTTORE:	Tinsley	UBICAZIONE:	Laboratorio MM (D; 208)
PROPRIETARIO:	INRIM	MESSA IN SERVIZIO:	2015
ELEMENTI:	Non applicabile		

INRIM ISTITUTO NAZIONALE DI RICERCA METROLOGICA		APPARECCHIATURE - SCHEDA EQUIPMENT - FORM	QT05_M03 Rev. 01 Pag. 1/2 Non controllato se stampato Uncontrolled if printed
DENOMINAZIONE:	Multimetro digitale		
Id. COSTRUTTORE:	s/n 2823A04175		
Id. ULTERIORE:	IEN-MA-ZNM-001		
DESCRIZIONE:	Lo strumento serve per misurare la tensione: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ai capi dei resistori campioni, ricavando, di conseguenza, la corrente elettrica; indotta in AC ai capi del secondario del magnetizzatore (Toro, EPSTEIN, SST). I valori di targa sono racchiusi nel manuale operativo.		
MODELLO/TIPO:	3458A	INVENTARIO:	--
COSTRUTTORE:	Hewlett Packard	UBICAZIONE:	Laboratorio MM (D; 208)
PROPRIETARIO:	INRIM	MESSA IN SERVIZIO:	1999
ELEMENTI:	NON APPLICABILE		

4) Epstein frames.

Epstein frame DC - 400 Hz

Epstein frame 400 Hz - 10 kHz

These frames are used for testing 30 mm wide 280-305 mm long strips, inserted as successive four-strip layers with overlapping corners. The Epstein frame for the measurements between DC and 400 Hz is endowed with $N_1 = 700$ turns and $N_2 = 700$ turns. It is built according to the IEC 60404-2 Standard (magnetic path length $l_m = 0.94$ m) and has built-in mutual inductor for air flux compensation. The Epstein frame for the measurements between 400 Hz and 10 kHz, is built instead with $N_1 = 200$ turns and $N_2 = 200$ turns, according to the IEC 60404-10 Standard. The turn-area is identified and the compensation for the air-flux is made mathematically via software. Non-oriented strips are inserted in both frame types by alternating in each layer two longitudinally-cut and two transversally-cut strips.

5) *SST magnetizer*. It is used for the measurements between DC and 400 Hz, according to the Standard IEC 60404-3, of 500 mm long and 300 mm – 500 mm wide sheets (magnetic path length $l_m = 0.45$ m). The INRIM SST magnetizer is a double-C core of 450 mm inner width, made of bent and resin bonded grain-oriented sheets. It is endowed with 202-turn and 382-turn primary and secondary windings, respectively, and with mutual inductor for automatic air-flux compensation. The upper yoke is movable upwards to permit insertion of the test specimen and is acted on by a suspension, by which its weight is counterbalanced up to a maximum vertical force of 200 N applied on the sheet. Non-oriented steel sheets are characterized by successively testing the sheet along the rolling and the transverse directions and averaging the results.

6) *SRS Low-noise amplifiers*. These devices are used under somewhat extreme conditions, with extremely low J_p values and frequencies. They are generally not needed for measurements for third parties and are not employed for intercomparisons. Specifications: 4 nV/ $\sqrt{\text{Hz}}$ input noise; 1 MHz bandwidth; variable gain from 1 to 50,000; 100 M Ω input impedance; 50 Ω output impedance; AC or DC coupled; Two configurable signal filters. The amplifiers gain, from $G = 1$ to $G = 20$, is calibrated up to 1 kHz using the Agilent 33220A as source of sinusoidal signal and the reference Agilent 3458A multimeter, by which the input and output signals of the amplifiers are measured. Table 3 makes a comparison between measured and nominal gains, as obtained by the calibration procedure. The amplifiers are in this case DC-coupled and the cutoff frequency is $f_c = 100$ kHz.

Frequency (Hz)	Nominal gain	G-SRS1-channel B	G-SRS2-channel H
10	1	1.001	0.990
	2	1.993	1.98
	5	4.987	4.96
	10	9.951	9.87
	20	19.91	19.72
20	1	1.001	0.990
	2	1.993	1.980
	5	4.984	4.96
	10	9.950	9.86
	20	19.89	19.71
60	1	1.001	0.990
	2	1.991	1.978
	5	4.98	4.96
	10	9.95	9.85
	20	19.89	19.70
400	1	0.998	0.988
	2	1.988	1.976
	5	4.97	4.95
	10	9.94	9.84
	20	19.87	19.67
1000	1	0.999	0.988
	2	1.988	1.97
	5	4.97	4.94
	10	9.94	9.83
	20	19.87	19.67

Table 3: Nominal versus actual gains of the SRS 560 low-noise amplifiers up to 1 kHz.

7) *LeCroy HDO4054 4-channel oscilloscope*. Specifications: 4 input channels; 12-bit ADC resolution; 10 GS/s sampling rate on 4 channels; Jitter between channels 2 ps rms; vertical accuracy $\pm 0,5 \% FS$; 500 MHz analogue bandwidth; input impedance 1 M Ω ; max input 400 V. The oscilloscope is subjected to periodic calibration (Tag: LCRY3509N07043, Technical procedure according to the operating manual).

INRIM ISTITUTO NAZIONALE DI RISPONSA METROLOGICA		APPARECCHIATURE - SCHEDA EQUIPMENT - FORM		QT05_M03 Rev. 00 Pag. 1/2 Non controllato se stampato Uncontrolled if printed
DENOMINAZIONE:	Oscilloscopio digitali			
Id. COSTRUTTORE:	LCRY3509N07043			
Id. ULTERIORE:	Wattmetro digitale INRIM			
DESCRIZIONE:	<p>Lo strumento appartiene alla catena di misura necessaria per effettuare le caratterizzazioni dei materiali magnetici in corrente alternata. In particolare, rileva due segnali:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • il primo è il segnale ai capi dell'avvolgimento secondario del magnetizzatore utilizzato per generare in C.M.; • il secondo è il segnale ai capi della resistenza di misura in serie con l'avvolgimento primario del magnetizzatore. <p>L'oscilloscopio essendo digitale è in grado di acquisire i dati, che vengono poi elaborati da un software applicativo.</p>			
MODELLO/TIPO:	HDO4054	INVENTARIO:	I.N.R.I.M. 0768.13	
COSTRUTTORE:	Le Croy	UBICAZIONE:	Laboratorio MM (D; 208)	
PROPRIETARIO:	INRIM	MESSA IN SERVIZIO:	novembre 2014	
ELEMENTI:	NON APPLICABILE			

8) *Dual-channel Keysight 33522A function generator*. This device is employed for the validation of the software in conjunction with the multimeter Agilent 3458A (see point 3)). It can generate precisely phase-shifted sinusoids through interlocked channels 1 and 2. Specifications: Frequency range 1 μ Hz to 30 MHz - 1 μ Hz resolution; 16-bit vertical resolution; output voltage: 20 V_{peak-to-peak} into infinite impedance load; relative phase: 0° to 360° with 0.1° resolution.

9) *Power amplifier Kepco BOP 50-20MG*. This bipolar power amplifier is used under circumstances where high currents are required. Specifications: max output voltage: $\pm 50 V$; max current: $\pm 20 A$; output impedance: 2.5 m Ω ; bandwidth: DC – 2 kHz.

10) *Power amplifier NF 4520*. This power amplifier is used under circumstances where high voltages are required up to 20 kHz. Specifications: rated output power: 2 kVA; max output voltage: ± 200 V; max rms current: 16.7 A; Voltage gain $G_V = 100$; bandwidth: DC – 20 kHz.

Figure 11: Flowchart of the procedure for the AC magnetic characterization of soft magnetic materials performed with the INRIM wattmeter-hysteresisgraph. The sequence of measuring steps, including the control of the induction waveform, is governed by a program developed within an Agilent-VEE PRO 7.0 software and now in Python.

Figure 12: The strong non-linearity of the hysteresis loop taken up to $J_p = 1.5$ T in a non-oriented Fe-Si sheet brings about relevant distortion of the secondary voltage $u_2(t)$ (channel 1 of the HD054 oscilloscope, yellow trace) when a sinusoidal function is programmed with the Agilent 33220A generator (see Fig. 16). Since a great deal of the loop area (energy loss) is the result of integration at low field values, the $u_H(t)$ signal is fed both into channel 2 (pink trace, full scale) and channel 3 (cyan trace, expanded scale).

Measuring uncertainty.

We provide here an approximate derivation of the measuring uncertainties associated with the main quantities measured with the wattmeter: magnetic field, magnetic polarization (induction), and energy loss. We shall refer to the standard measurements, which are made without the use of the SRS low-noise amplifiers. We shall also distinguish between type A (repeatability) and Type B (systematic) contributions. The former depends on the number of measurements performed under the very same conditions. The type B depends on the calibration and resolution of the involved instrumentation and devices and on the possible drift and instability of the measuring conditions (in order to avoid confusion with the standard notation u for the uncertainty, we use in this sub-section, the symbol V for the voltages).

1) Magnetic field. According to the relationship $H = (N_l/l_m) \cdot V_H/R_H$, we shall relate the systematic uncertainty on H to the one associated with the voltage drop V_H and the reference shunt R_H . To note that a systematic correction for the gains of channel 2 and channel 3 of the HDO 4054 of 0.2 % is introduced, following their calibration, in the calculation software. What remains is the uncertainty on this correction. We write then the combined standard relative uncertainty as

$$\frac{u_H}{H} = \sqrt{\frac{u_A^2(H)}{H^2} + \frac{u_B^2(V_H)}{V_H^2} + \frac{u_B^2(R_H)}{R_H^2}}. \quad (12)$$

The uncertainty terms $u_B^2(V_H)$ and $u_B^2(R_H)$ include possible contributions from changing temperature.

It is sometimes necessary to provide the uncertainty of the peak field value associated with a defined polarization value. In this specific case we shall need to explicitly consider the dependence of H_p (that is, of V_H) on J_p and especially the fact that at very high induction values the field is subjected to increasingly large variations for a same variation of J . The relative uncertainty (12) becomes

$$\frac{u_H}{H} = \sqrt{\frac{u_A^2(H)}{H^2} + \frac{u_B^2(V_H)}{V_H^2} + \frac{u_B^2(R_H)}{R_H^2} + \left(\frac{\partial H}{\partial J}\right)^2 \cdot \left(\frac{J}{H}\right)^2 \frac{u_B^2(J)}{J^2}}. \quad (13)$$

2) Magnetic polarization. We note again that the calibration of channel 1 of the HDO 4054 calls for a correction of the gain of this channel of 0.2 %. We can assume an uncertainty on this correction of 0.1 %. We write

$$\frac{u_J}{J} = \sqrt{\frac{u_A^2(J)}{J^2} + \frac{u_B^2(V_2)}{V_2^2} + \frac{u_B^2(S)}{S^2} + \frac{u_B^2(J_a)}{J^2}}, \quad (14)$$

where $u_B(S)$ is the uncertainty on the cross-sectional area of the sample and $u_B(J_a)$ derives from possible imperfect compensation of the air-flux.

3) Magnetic energy loss. Since we are dealing with sinusoidal polarization and the cross-products of the harmonics of the magnetic field with $J(t)$ integrate to zero, we can simplify the whole treatment by writing the energy loss as $W(J_p) = \pi J_p H_{p1} \sin\varphi$ [J/m³], where H_{p1} is the peak value of the fundamental harmonic of $H(t)$ and φ is the phase shift between the fundamental harmonic of $H(t)$ and $J(t)$. We write for the combined relative uncertainty of the energy loss at a given peak value J_p of the sinusoidal polarization

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{u(W)}{W} &= \sqrt{\frac{u_A^2(W)}{W^2} + \left(\frac{\partial W}{\partial J_p} \frac{u_B(J_p)}{W}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial W}{\partial H_{p1}} \frac{u_B(H_{p1})}{W}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial W}{\partial \varphi} \frac{u_B(\varphi)}{W}\right)^2} = \\ &= \sqrt{\frac{u_A^2(W)}{W^2} + \frac{u_B^2(J_p)}{J_p^2} + \frac{u_B^2(H_{p1})}{H_{p1}^2} + (\varphi \cdot \text{ctg}\varphi \cdot \frac{u_B(\varphi)}{\varphi})^2}. \end{aligned} \quad (15)$$

It is apparent in this equation the surge of uncertainty occurring on approaching very low phase shifts between field and polarization (extremely narrow hysteresis loops).

2.4 – Validation

The validation of the developed software and of the results achieved by the measuring setup as a whole is carried out by a simulation involving a couple of calibrated sinusoidal waveforms with precisely defined phase shifts and by making a series of measurements on different steel sheets either through bilateral comparisons or IEC-TC68 round robins.

Channel 1 and Channel 2 of the HDO 4054 oscilloscope are fed by two sinusoidal waveforms having identical amplitude and precisely defined phase shift. The waveforms, supplied by the Keysight 33522A function generator, are measured by the calibrated Agilent 3458 multimeter and precisely set to 1.000 V peak value. The accuracy of the measurement, taken after suitably long warm up, is better than 10⁻⁴. The resolution of the phase shift θ between the generated sinusoids is 0.1°. By feeding two oscilloscope channels by the very same sinusoid and by both of them with nominal 0° phase shift and making channel inversion, the uncertainty on the θ value is estimated around $\pm 0.01^\circ$. The oscilloscope channels are set full scale. Checks are made at half-scale and 1/4 of full scale. After verifying the calibration of the oscilloscope gain and imposing the corrections $\text{Gain}_{\text{ch1}} = 1.002$, $\text{Gain}_{\text{ch2}} = 0.998$, $\text{Gain}_{\text{ch3}} = 0.998$, acquisition, A/D conversion, and signal handling by software are performed for a sequence of phase shifts running from 0° through 90° between the two waveforms. In this way we emulate the secondary voltage (Channel 1) and the voltage drop on the shunt resistor R_H (Channel 2 and 3). Under these conditions, the software should provide the equivalent values $H_p = 1$ A/m, $J_p = 3.183 \cdot 10^{-3}$ T, energy loss $W(J_p) = (1/2f) \cdot \cos\theta$ (J/m³).

The results of the simulation are listed in the following Table 4.

The difference between the theoretically calculated energy loss values W_{theor} and the values obtained by software W_{meas} , emulating the actual loss measurements, is always negligible, but for phase shift θ between the signals (equivalent to the $H(t)$ and dJ/dt signals) less than 0.5°, that is with the signals close to quadrature. In addition, by limiting the signal amplitude on the HDO 4054 channels to either half scale or 1/4th of full scale we do not appreciably change the results provided by the software.

Phase θ ($^\circ$)	$J_{p,\text{meas}}$ (T)	$H_{p,\text{meas}}$ (A/m)	W_{theor} (J/m ³)	W_{meas} (J/m ³)	$W_{\text{meas,hres}}$ (J/m ³)
0	3.1823	1.0000	$1.000 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$9.999 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$9.997 \cdot 10^{-3}$
10	3.1825	1.0000	$9.84 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$9.852 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$9.848 \cdot 10^{-3}$
20	3.1831	1.0000	$9.40 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$9.40 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$9.397 \cdot 10^{-3}$
30	3.1826	1.0000	$8.660 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$8.663 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$8.660 \cdot 10^{-3}$
40	3.1829	0.9999	$7.660 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$7.663 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$7.661 \cdot 10^{-3}$
50	3.1832	1.0002	$6.430 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$6.430 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$6.431 \cdot 10^{-3}$
60	3.1816	1.0000	$5.000 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$5.000 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$4.999 \cdot 10^{-3}$
70	3.1827	1.0000	$3.420 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$3.423 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$3.420 \cdot 10^{-3}$
80	3.1827	1.0000	$1.736 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$1.739 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$1.737 \cdot 10^{-3}$
80 - halfscale	3.1835	0.9998	$1.736 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$1.736 \cdot 10^{-3}$	-----
85	3.1833	1.0000	$8.72 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$8.733 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$8.730 \cdot 10^{-4}$
87	3.1830	1.0000	$5.23 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$5.25 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$5.258 \cdot 10^{-4}$
88	3.1820	1.0000	$3.490 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$3.504 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$3.502 \cdot 10^{-4}$
88 - halfscale	3.1860	0.9990	$3.490 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$3.495 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$3.505 \cdot 10^{-4}$
88 -1/4 th scale	3.1820	1.001	$3.490 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$3.484 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$3.492 \cdot 10^{-4}$
88.5	3.1830	0.9999	$2.618 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$2.631 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$2.632 \cdot 10^{-4}$
89	3.1833	1.0001	$1.745 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$1.765 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$1.760 \cdot 10^{-4}$
89.5	3.1830	1.0000	$8.73 \cdot 10^{-5}$	$8.86 \cdot 10^{-5}$	$8.88 \cdot 10^{-5}$
89.8	3.1832	1.0001	$3.49 \cdot 10^{-5}$	$3.64 \cdot 10^{-5}$	$3.55 \cdot 10^{-5}$
90	3.1830	1.0000	0	$7.86 \cdot 10^{-7}$	$16.3 \cdot 10^{-7}$

Table 4: Software validation is performed by emulating the experimental $u_2(t)$ and $u_H(t)$ functions by means of precisely measured sinusoidal voltages of peak amplitude $V_p = 1.000$ V.

While confidently relying on the developed measuring approach, it appears quite important to resort to a validation based on comparisons. This objective has been reached both by bilateral comparisons with metrological labs and by the participation in international round robins. A few significant results are provided below. Table 6 reports the results of a recent comparison carried out with Centro Nacional de Metrologia in Querétaro, Mexico on the power loss at 50 Hz in grain-oriented and non-oriented Fe-Si Epstein strips.

Grain-oriented Fe-Si Epstein strips							
Peak magnetic polarization ($J_p \pm U$) T		Specific power loss ($P_s \pm U$) W/kg		Apparent power loss ($S_s \pm U$) VA/kg		Form Factor FF	
INRIM	CENAM	INRIM	CENAM	INRIM	CENAM	INRIM	CENAM
1.4997 ± 0.0075	1.501 ± 0.003	0.845 ± 0.013	0.85 \pm 0.002	1.01 ± 0.02	1.01 ± 0.01	1.1109 $\pm 1 \%$	1.1109 $\pm 0.02 \%$
1.700 ± 0.0085	1.7 ± 0.004	1.1695 \pm 0.018	1.174 \pm 0.002	1.955 ± 0.04	2.014 ± 0.02	1.1109 $\pm 1 \%$	1.1107 $\pm 0.01 \%$
Non-oriented Fe-Si Epstein strips							
Peak magnetic polarization ($J_p \pm U$) T		Specific power loss ($P_s \pm U$) W/kg		Apparent power loss ($S_s \pm U$) VA/kg		Form Factor FF	
INRIM	CENAM	INRIM	CENAM	INRIM	CENAM	INRIM	CENAM
0.9991 ± 0.005	1.000 \pm 0.002	1.154 ± 0.017	1.15 ± 0.003	1.727 ± 0.52	1.769 ± 0.021	1.1109 $\pm 1 \%$	1.1109 $\pm 0.03 \%$
1.5005 ± 0.0075	1.501 \pm 0.003	2.961 ± 0.044	2.917 ± 0.006	21.70 ± 0.65	23.03 ± 0.41	1.1105 $\pm 1 \%$	1.1129 $\pm 0.02 \%$

Table 5: Power losses and the apparent power in grain-oriented and non-oriented Fe-Si sheets measured at different J_p values and 50 Hz by the magnetics labs at CENAM (Mexico) and INRIM are compared.

The following figures illustrate a few results on power losses and apparent power obtained along an international comparison carried out in the framework of the activity of the IEC-TC68. This comparison, carried out along the years 2013-2014, involved 10 different laboratories from metrological Institutes and industry in Europe and Asia. It was devoted to measurements on five different types of grain-oriented Fe-Si sheets by the Epstein and the SST methods. INRIM organized this comparison as pilot lab.

Figure 13: Example of scattering of the laboratories best estimates around the reference value (unweighted average, dash-dotted line). The reported values of power loss P and apparent power S refer to the SST and Epstein measurements in a CGO sample at $J_p = 1.7$ T and $f = 50$ Hz. (PL is the pilot laboratory). The dashed line indicates the reference value. The yellow circles show the results obtained by the INRIM wattmeter.

Figure 14: As in Fig. 13 above for the HGO sample

3.4 Measurement setup at NPL

The measurement set-up for determination of specific total loss at NPL is based on the wattmeter method outlined in IEC 60404-2, -3, -10. Figure 15 shows a schematic of the measurement set-up used for both the Epstein frame and single sheet tester.

Figure 15: Setup for measurement of specific total loss at NPL.

For determination of the peak magnetic polarization an alternative measurement set-up was used. In this case the peak magnetic field strength was determined using a mutual inductor. In this set-up the primary coil was connected in series with the current source and the primary coil of a calibrated mutual inductor, while the secondary coil was connected to two calibrated voltmeters. The peak magnetic field strength was determined by measuring the voltage across the secondary coil of the mutual inductor. The measurement set-up is shown in Figure 16.

Figure 16: Setup for measurement of peak magnetic polarization at NPL.

Dependent on the frequency, two Epstein frames were used during the measurements. For frequencies between 50 Hz and 400 Hz, the frame consisted of 160 turns on the primary coil

and 480 turns on the secondary coil. The mutual inductor, which compensates for the air flux compensation was not included in the circuit for this frame. A manual air flux correction was applied to the data. This is discussed further in Section 4. The second frame was used for measurements at 400 Hz and above, which had 100 turns on both the primary and secondary coils and included the compensating mutual inductor.

For both measurement systems a digital feedback system is used to generate the AC waveform and control the feedback to ensure the secondary waveform remains sinusoidal as outline by the measurement standard. The feedback is based on a PID system which compared the measured secondary waveform to a predicted waveform for a specific magnetic polarisation.

Uncertainty budget for NPL measurements

The overall measurement uncertainty was calculated as outlined in reference [14]. A typical uncertainty budget for specific total power loss at 50 Hz is given in Table 6. A typical measurement uncertainty for peak magnetic polarization is given in Table 7.

Uncertainty budget for SST at 50 Hz and 1.5 T						
Source of Uncertainty	Value ± %	Probability distribution	Diviso r	c _i	u _i ± %	V _i or V _{eff}
Cross sectional area uncertainty	0.0851	normal	2	1	0.0425	Inf.
Measurement of frequency	0.0074	normal	2	2	0.0074	Inf.
Calibration of Wattmeter	0.017	normal	2	1	0.0087	Inf.
Error in Wattmeter	0.005	rectangular	1.732 1	1	0.0031	Inf.
Resolution of Power Measurements	0.001	rectangular	1.732 1	1	0.0003	Inf.
Temperature Coefficient	0.05	rectangular	1.732 1	1	0.0289	Inf.
Form Factor	0.1026	rectangular	1.732 1	1.5	0.00889	Inf.
Digital Phase correction	0.20	rectangular	1.732 1	1	0.1155	Inf.
Power Factor below 1	0.30	rectangular	1.732 1	1	0.1732	Inf.
Uncertainty in magnetic polarisation	0.107	normal	2	1.6 2	0.0869	Inf.
Repeatability of Loss measurements	0.0573	normal	1	1	0.0573	2
Standard uncertainty (± %)		<i>k</i> = 1			0.2547	758
Expanded uncertainty (± %)		<i>k</i> = 2			0.5093	

Table 6: Typical uncertainty budget for specific power loss at NPL.

Uncertainty budget for SST at $J(H)$						
Source of Uncertainty	Value $\pm \%$	Probability distribution	Divisor	c_i	u_i $\pm \%$	V_i or V_{eff}
Calibration of frequency meter	0.0035	normal	2	1	0.001 8	inf.
Resolution of frequency counter	0.002	rectangular	1.7321	1	0.001 1	inf.
Repeatability of frequency counter	0.000	normal	1	1	0.000 2	9
Calibration of DMM	0.090	normal	2	2	0.900 0	inf.
Resolution of DMM (Measuring H)	0.160	rectangular	1.7321	1	0.092 2	inf.
Resolution of DMM (Measuring J)	0.037	rectangular	1.7321	1	0.021 1	inf.
Digital Phase correction	0.300	rectangular	1.7321	1	0.173 2	inf.
Calibration of mutual inductor	0.021	normal	2	1	0.010 5	inf.
Standard uncertainty ($\pm \%$)	$k = 1$				0.202 8	5968873
Expanded uncertainty ($\pm \%$)	$k = 2$				0.405 5	

Table 7: Typical uncertainty budget for peak magnetic polarization at NPL.

The quantities that appear in NPL's UKAS (United Kingdom accreditation service) scope are presented in Table 8. These are accredited to ISO/IEC 17025:2017.

Measured Quantity	Range	Base Measurement Uncertainty ($k = 2$)	Frequency Range	Magnetic Polarisation Range
Specific Total Power Loss	0.02 W/kg to 400 W/kg	0.4 %	50 Hz to 2 kHz	0.1 T to 1.3 T
		0.40 %	50 Hz to 1 kHz	1.3 T to 1.5 T
		0.55 %		1.5 T to 1.7 T
		0.75 %		1.7 T to 1.8 T
		1.0 %		1.8 T to 1.9 T
		0.65 %	50 Hz to 100 kHz	1 mT to 100 mT
Specific Apparent Power	0.06 VA/kg to 450 VA/kg	0.60 %	50 Hz to 2 kHz	0.1 T to 1.3 T
		0.70 %	50 Hz to 1 kHz	1.3 T to 1.5 T
		1.3 %		1.5 T to 1.7 T
		2.7 %		1.7 T to 1.8 T
		5.0 %		1.8 T to 1.9 T
		1.1 T	50 Hz to 100 kHz	1 mT to 100 mT
Peak Magnetic Polarization	0.5 T to 2.2 T	0.45 %	50 Hz, 60 Hz	-

Table 8: Calibration and capabilities accredited to ISO/IEC 17025

4 Measurement Challenges

- Differences between the measurement with 700 turns Epstein frame and 100 turns Epstein frame above 100 Hz [13]: depending on the setup used there can be a significant difference when using the 700 turns frame above 100 Hz. From the HEFMAG comparison it seems that using 100 turns Epstein frame is better choice for frequencies above 100 Hz. This issue can also be connected to the high voltages observed at the secondary of the Epstein frame which may induce a small but not negligible current flow in the secondary circuit
- Specific care should be taken in the calibration and evaluation of phase shifts due to amplifiers, attenuators or shunts. In general, the presence of multiple components for the measurement of loss in different ranges may lead to additional uncertainty sources, which should be estimated beforehand and properly compensated.
- Temperature - issues can occur, when the environment temperature is outside the range stated in the IEC standard. The standard states the measurements should be made $23\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C} \pm 5\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. It was verified that outside of this range an additional systematic measurement uncertainty should be included.
- Loss measurements (and the associated loops) need to be performed ensuring a “single shot” acquisition of the H and dB/dt waveforms over a single period, without any averaging. Averaging the waveforms over several measurement periods will mask the stochastic nature of the hysteresis phenomenon and may lead, depending on the type of material, to significant additional uncertainties. A loss average can only be obtained by averaging the results of several single shot one period measurements.
- Measurement of J_m at $H_m=800\text{ A/m}$ (J800) and $H_m=2500\text{ A/m}$ (J2500) also need to be performed as single shot experiments. The vertices of the loops obtained should then form a cloud of points from which and uncertainty in H and J can be derived
- Measurements of magnetostrictive Epstein strips should be performed taking particular care in the positioning of the Epstein strips in the circuit, allowing the cyclical deformation of the strips, while avoiding large strip motions due to the vibrations
- When the mutual inductor wasn't correcting the air flux, the magnetic flux density B is measured instead of the magnetic polarisation, J . the air flux correction can be applied according to:

$$B_{act} = B_{meas} - \left(\left(\frac{A_w - A_s}{A_s} \right) \mu_0 H \right) \quad (16)$$

And then converted to J by:

$$J = B_{act} - \mu_0 H \quad (17)$$

Where:

B_{act}	=	actual magnetic flux density (T)
B_{meas}	=	measured magnetic flux density (T)
A_W	=	cross sectional area of windings (m ²)
A_s	=	cross sectional area of sample (m ²)
H	=	magnetic field strength (A/m)
J	=	magnetic polarization (T)

The cross-sectional area of the winding can be determined from the dimensions of the Epstein frame. This was compared to measurements where the effective area of the coil was determined from a mutual inductance bridge method. There was a small difference between the two methods, both were within the measurement uncertainty. The value determined through the mutual inductance bridge was used for the correction during the HEFMAG comparison.

The air flux results in a smaller magnetic polarisation compared to the target polarisation. During the measurements a number of points are taken either side of each measurement point to determine the power loss gradient. This gradient and the calculated change in field was used to apply a correction to the measured power loss value.

- changing sample properties by different demagnetization

(IEC 60404-6-2003 Prior to measurement, the test specimen shall be carefully demagnetized from a value of field strength of not less than ten times the coercivity by slowly reducing the corresponding magnitude of the magnetizing current to zero. Demagnetization shall be carried out at the same or lower frequency as will be used for the measurements.) In our case it was chosen to use 50 Hz.

- metastable domain states

Can be found if different demagnetization procedures are used, so the same procedure should be used.

- form factor description versus harmonic distortion factor

Maybe can be used but right now this comparison is not prescribed by normative.

- asymmetric hysteresis curves and implications for the measurement

The loop must be as symmetric as possible. Single shot acquisitions may help to determine which loops can be used to determine the average loss and which should be discarded, being too asymmetric.

5 Traceability

For measurement accuracy to be consistent regardless of the individual, time of measurement or location of measurement, traceability to rigorously maintained measurement standards are required. Traceability requires an unbroken chain of measurements where the primary measurement is usually carried out by the national standards laboratory of the country where the measurements are performed (e.g. CMI in Czechia, INRIM in Italy, PTB in Germany, NPL in United Kingdom). The national standards laboratories are generally, but not exclusively, the pinnacle of each country's measurement pyramid where the lowest measurement uncertainties are offered. The primary standards maintained by the national standards laboratories are then used to calibrate instruments and materials from the next tier of the pyramid, accredited laboratories, which have been accredited to conform to international standard ISO/IEC 17025 [15].

International comparisons such as [4, 5] were conducted to establish the NMI equivalence.

6 European capabilities for power losses

Information about each national laboratory measurement capabilities in the area of specific power losses can be found at the BIPM website:

<https://www.bipm.org/>

Specific information can be found on the 'Calibration and Measurement Capabilities' (CMC's) database (KCDB):

<https://www.bipm.org/kcdb/cmc/advanced-search>

Using the advanced search drop down menu select:

Metrology area:	Electricity and Magnetism (EM)
Branch:	Materials
Service:	Measurements on materials
Sub-service:	Soft magnetic sheet and powder materials

Individual service: Specific total power loss

Table 9 below gives a brief breakdown of the specific total power loss measurement of the laboratories taking part in the EMRP 2020 Joint Research Project ‘Metrology of magnetic losses in electrical steel sheets for high-efficiency energy conversion’ (HEFMAG).

Measurement range	BMC ($k=2$)	Frequency range
Czech Republic – CMI		
0.2 to 200 W/kg	0.5 %	50 Hz to 400 Hz
	0.7 %	400 Hz to 1000 Hz
Germany – PTB		
0.1 to 100 W/kg	0.1 % to 2 %	16 Hz to 400 Hz
Italy – INRIM		
0.005 to 200 W/kg	2 %	1 Hz to 10 Hz
	1 %	10 Hz to 1 kHz
	2 %	1 kHz to 10 kHz
United Kingdom - NPL		
0.02 to 400 W/kg	0.40%	50 Hz to 2 kHz, 0.1 T to 1.3 T
	0.40%	50 Hz to 1 kHz, 1.3 T to 1.5 T
	0.55%	1.5 T to 1.7 T
	0.75%	1.7 T to 1.8 T
	1.0%	1.8 T to 1.9 T

Table 9: Specific total power loss measurement capabilities

The following countries have entries on the BIPM CMC database for specific total power loss:

Country	NMI	Website
China	NIM	http://www.nim.ac.cn/
Czech Republic	CMI	http://www.cmi.cz/
Germany	PTB	http://www.ptb.de/
Italy	INRIM	http://www.inrim.it/
Russian Federation	VNIIM	http://www.vniim.ru/
United Kingdom	NPL	http://www.npl.co.uk/

Table 10: Countries that have entries on the BIPM CMC database for specific total power loss

7 References

- [1] IEC 60404-2 Magnetic materials - Part 2: Methods of measurement of the magnetic properties of electrical steel sheet and strip by means of an Epstein frame
- [2] IEC 60404-10 Magnetic materials - Part 10: Methods of measurement of magnetic properties of electrical steel strip and sheet at medium frequencies
- [3] IEC 60404-3 Magnetic materials - Part 3: Methods of measurement of the magnetic properties of electrical steel strip and sheet by means of a single sheet tester
- [4] M. Ulvr et al.: “Comparisons of total power loss measurements performed by Epstein frame using revised procedures at room temperature – Final report”, 2023.
- [5] M. Ulvr et al.: “Comparisons of total power loss measurements performed by an SST using revised measurement procedures at room temperature - Final report”, 2023.
- [6] J. Lüdke and H. Ahlers: “Hybrid control used to obtain sinusoidal curve form for the power loss measurement on magnetic materials”, *Materials Science Forum*, vol. 373 - 376, 2001, pp. 469-472.
- [7] J. Lüdke et al.: “Experimental setup for the measurement of power losses in electrical steel sheets at PTB”, to be published (2023).
- [8] A. Hubert and R. Schäfer: “Magnetic domains”, Springer, Berlin, 1998, p. 184.
- [9] J. Sievert: “Recent advances in the one- and two-dimensional magnetic measurement technique for electrical sheet steel”, *IEEE Trans. Magn.*, vol. 26, no. 5, 1990, pp. 2553-2558.
- [10] C. Appino, E. Ferrara, F. Fiorillo, L. Rocchino, C. Ragusa, J. Sievert, T. Belgrand, C. Wang, P. Denke, S. Siebert, Y. Norgren, K. Gramm, S. Norman, R. Lyke, M. Albrecht, X. Zhou, W. Fan, X. Guo, M. Hall, “International comparison on SST and Epstein measurements in grain-oriented Fe-Si sheet steel,” *International Journal of Applied Electromagnetics and Mechanics*, vol. 48, no. 2-3, pp. 123 – 133, 2015.
- [11] E. Ferrara, C. Appino, L. Rocchino, C. Ragusa, O. de la Barrière, F. Fiorillo, “Effective versus standard Epstein loss figure in Fe-Si sheets”, *International Journal of Applied Electromagnetics and Mechanics*, vol. 55, no. S1, 2017, pp. 105-112.
- [12] IEC 60404-6 Methods of measurement of the magnetic properties of magnetically soft metallic and powder materials at frequencies in the range 20 Hz to 200 kHz by the use of ring specimens.
- [13] M. Pasquale, C. Susso, M. Velluto and G. Bertotti: “Circuit and Field Interaction in Hysteretic Media: Part II) Medium Frequency Behavior of the Epstein Measurement Circuit”, Proc. of ISEM '99, 2000, pp. 73-76.
- [14] H. Ahlers and J. Lüdke: “The uncertainty of magnetic properties measurements of electrical sheet steel”, *Journal of Magnetism and Magnetic Materials*, vol. 215-216, pp. 711-713, 2000.
- [15] ISO/IEC 17025 General requirements for the competence of testing and calibration laboratories.